

BULLYING, AGGRESSION AND HARASSMENT IN SCHOOL AND UNIVERSITY: A LESSON FROM ZULFARHAN OSMAN ZULKARNAIN CASE

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Abstract

The issue of bullying, aggression and harassment always becoming a hot topic of discussion in our daily life. Bullying, aggression and harassment can happen anywhere and at any times. Bullying, aggression and harassment can happen at the workplaces, on roads, inside public transports, within family, between friends and many more. Bullying, aggression and harassment can also happen in the educational sector like in school and university. Unlike the act of bullying, aggression and harassment which happen in other avenues, bullying, aggression and harassment which happen in the educational sectors should be received serious attention by everyone because it involves young people who are relatively unaware over the right to protect themselves from any forms of misbehaviours and attitudes and the inability to find ways to seek the necessary help if they become the victim of bullying, aggression and harassment. No one should take bullying, aggression and harassment issue lightly. For the last many years, there has been several reported news over the incident of bullying, aggression and harassment which happen in the school in the country. However, the time has come for us to change our mind set and attitude when it comes to the issue on bullying, aggression and harassment. Many people in the country still think bullying, aggression and harassment only happen to kids in schools. Bullying, aggression and harassment can happen to anyone regardless of their age, gender and it can also happen in the university. In 2017, the whole country was shocked over the tragic death of Zulfarhan Osman Zulkarnain, 21-year-old university student. The 21-year-old undergraduate student passed away at Serdang Hospital after sustained serious injuries suspected of being subjected to bullying, aggression and harassment by his university colleagues. On 23 July 2024, the country Court of Appeal has reinstated the murder charge under Section 302 of the Penal Code for six former students for causing the death of Zulfarhan Osman Zulkarnain, seven years ago. The court panel had rejected the conviction for causing death by negligence under Section 304(a) of the Penal Code and the 18-year prison sentences previously given by the nation High Court. Many experts have recognized that bullying, aggression and harassment can happen anywhere and at any time, university compound is no exception. Just because no one have actively talk about it, it does not mean that it does not exist. There is social stigma deeply rooted in many societies that believe bullying, aggression and harassment don't happen in the university due to the reason that university student is smart and mature enough not to get involved with any bullying, aggression and harassment attitude. As such, the matter goes unnoticed and unchecked for many years. There is no single cause which creates bullying, aggression and harassment. Bullying, aggression and harassment happen due to many reasons. At the same time, there are various types of bullying, aggression and harassment. With the advancement of technology, the act of bullying, aggression and harassment can happen through online. Regardless the causes or types of bullying, aggression and harassment, such acts can cause serious harm to the victim and their family. It is very important for us to examine the issue seriously and take steps to prevent bullying, aggression and harassment from becoming out of control in the educational sector in the country. Thus, it is the object of this paper to examine the issue of bullying, aggression and harassment in the educational sector closely and locate any possible solutions to address such issue comprehensively and effectively.

Keywords: Bullying, Aggression, Harassment, School, University

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The issue of bullying, aggression and harassment have become dominant topic of discussion all over the world including in Malaysia. The act of bullying, aggression and harassment happen to many peoples in all countries. Malaysia is no exception to it. Such issues have become a major problem to many peoples. Many steps have been taken to address and tackle with the issue of bullying, aggression and harassment either through legislations as well as through awareness campaigns organized by the government and the non – governmental organizations (NGOs). Though these problems always became a dominant topic of discussion among adult, it also has started to influence young adult namely the children and adolescent. Over the years, many reported cases over bullying, aggression and harassment among children and adolescent in schools and universities. The most well-known involving bullying, aggression and harassment involved one local university student by the name of Zulfarhan Osman Zulkarnain. He was found died believed to be the victim of bullying, aggression and harassment from his own university colleagues. A brief fact about his tragic death can be highlighted as the following. Between 21 and 22 May 2017, 20-year-old Zulfarhan Osman Zulkarnain (29 November 1996 – 1 June 2017), a military cadet officer of National Defence University of Malaysia (UPNM), was relentlessly tortured and scalded with a steam iron at the university's hostel by his fellow students over a stolen laptop, and died from multiple injuries at Serdang Hospital on 1 June 2017. A total of 18 students, all male, were arrested and out of these 18 suspects, six of them were charged with murder and assault while the remaining 12 were charged with assaulting and hurting Zulfarhan. A 19TH suspect was originally charged with causing hurt to the victim but was acquitted without having his defence being called. After a long-drawn trial process from 29 January 2018 to 2 November 2021, the country Kuala Lumpur High Court found the six main perpetrators guilty of manslaughter instead of murder, and sentenced them to 18 years' imprisonment each, while the remaining 12 were sentenced to three years in jail each for causing hurt to Zulfarhan. However, upon the prosecution's appeal on 23 July 2024, the Court of Appeal found the six main offenders guilty of murder and sentenced them to death, after finding that the murder itself was among the "rarest of the rare" cases and the six had exhibited a blatant disregard for human life, and hence the death penalty was the only appropriate sentence for the six. The respective three-year jail terms of the 12 other accomplices were raised to four years for each of them. (Nurbaiti Hamdan, 2024). This tragic incident has received wide attention among the Malaysian public. The Malaysian public demands action to be taken to put an end to bullying, aggression and harassment among pupil in the educational sector. While many still grieving over the tragic incident involving Zulfarhan Osman Zulkarnain, another incident being reported involving students belonging to the same university. In a statement on Sunday (Nov 10, 2024), Kuala Lumpur police chief Comm Datuk Rusdi Mohd Isa said that a report on the alleged bullying was lodged at around 8.40pm on Nov 8, 2024. The report said that the victim, a Year One student at the university, had been injured on Oct 21, 2024 after roll call at the field at the university. "The 19-year-old victim is reported to have suffered from fractured ribs and spine after he was stepped on by a Year Three student. The victim is still being treated for the injuries. "The case is being investigated under Section 325 of the Penal Code," he said. He also urged all quarters not to speculate on the incident as investigations are still ongoing. On Nov 8, 2024, a cadet from the university had claimed trial at the Sessions Court here to causing hurt to a junior using a steam iron. Amirul Iskandar Norhanizan, 22, pleaded not guilty after the charge was read out to him by the interpreter before Judge Egusra Ali. According to the charge sheet, Amirul Iskandar allegedly voluntarily caused hurt to Muhammad Salman Mohd Saiful Surash, 20, by using a hot steam iron. He was accused of committing the offence in a dormitory room at the military academy, at about 11.45pm on Oct 22, 2024. (Justin Zack, 2024). While many were shocked over this latest incident, the country was exposed with another shocked over alleged college dorm assault which happen in another local university. According to the media, on 19 December 2024, twelve Universiti Malaysia Terengganu (UMT) students have been remanded for four days to assist in investigations into the alleged assault of a fellow student, which reportedly caused him serious injuries. The Kuala Terengganu Magistrate's Court approved the remand order after the students were arrested following the incident, believed to have taken place in the early hours of Sunday at the UMT Male Residential College. Police said the 21-year-old victim, an accounting student, claimed he was beaten in turns, strangled, kicked, punched, and struck with a blunt object. A wooden stick, believed to have been used in the assault, has been seized as evidence. Terengganu Police Chief Datuk Mohd Khairi Khairuddin told the media that preliminary findings suggest the incident stemmed from accusations made against the victim. "The fight may have been triggered by accusations against the victim involving conduct contrary to human norms, but I won't specify the allegations," he was quoted as saying. Medical reports revealed the victim sustained bruises but no internal injuries or fractures. "The victim remains

under observation,” Mohd Khairi confirmed. He added that urine tests conducted on all 12 suspects returned negative results for drugs. The victim contacted his parents in Melaka after the incident, and they took him to the Emergency Department of Sultanah Nur Zahirah Hospital in Kuala Terengganu for treatment. The case is being investigated under Section 148 of the Penal Code for rioting with weapons. (Malay Mail, 2024).

There are other notorious bullying, aggression and harassment cases which get huge attention from the Malaysian public for the last many years. Among it includes the tragic death of T. Nhaveen. On June 10, 2017, T. Nhaveen, 18, and his friend T. Previin, 19, were attacked at a local burger stall. The confrontation escalated into violence, with Nhaveen forcibly taken to a field where he was brutally beaten, burned with cigarettes and sexually assaulted. Five suspects, aged 16 to 18, were detained following the incident. Despite medical evidence confirming Nhaveen succumbed to his injuries, including blunt force trauma, days later, the Penang High Court acquitted the five suspects in October 2023. Justice Radzi Hamid cited inconsistencies in the evidence and deemed key witness Previin's account unreliable. The suspects were also discharged from a second charge of causing grievous hurt to Previin due to the same credibility issues. The acquitted individuals are S. Gopinaath, 32, J. Ragesuthan, 24, S. Gokulan, 24, V. Sharmah, 24, and K. Tatisan, 23, who were initially charged with jointly murdering Nhaveen at Jalan Bunga Raya between 11pm and midnight on June 9, 2017. (Aundrey Dermawan, 2023). Another tragic case involving the death of 23 residents in one religious' school (Madrassa). The 2017 Darul Quran Ittifaqiyah madrasa fire occurred around 5:10 a.m. on September 14, 2017, when a fire broke out at the Darul Quran Ittifaqiyah madrasa in Kampung Datuk Keramat, Kuala Lumpur, resulting in the deaths of 23 madrasa residents, comprising 21 students and two teachers, while five others were reportedly injured. (Rozanna Latiff and A. Ananthalakshmi, 2017 and Salhan K. Ahmad, King Chai Woon and Sandi Sidhu, 2017). Investigations revealed that a quarrel had erupted between the madrasa boarders and a group of seven teenage boys who entered the area to abuse drugs they had purchased. This altercation prompted the teens to set fire to the building. All seven troubled teens had been expelled from school following numerous serious disciplinary offenses. Additional factors included a firework assault against the madrasa boarders by the same teens and a dispute over the use of the futsal court between the two parties. (Faisza Roslan, 2017). Investigations were conducted by the police and firefighters to determine the cause of the fire. Initially, the firefighters thought it might be due to a short circuit, but after a full investigation and through Closed-Circuit Television (CCTV) footage outside the building, several suspects were identified as having infiltrated the area around 3:10 am. Other CCTV footage retrieved from the five nearest petrol stations showed the intruding suspects earlier buying petrol at one of the stations at 1:30 am on a Yamaha Lagenda motorcycle. Around seven suspects were identified by police to be involved, and most of them were apprehended on September 16, 2017, and detained at the Jinjang Police Station lock-up. Survivors were detained at the Ministry of Defence tent set up outside the madrasa before being placed in secret premises around Keramat on September 15. The number of survivors was also kept confidential, and only the closest relatives were allowed to enter the premises to protect them from being approached by the public. Kuala Lumpur Police Chief Amar Singh concluded in a special press conference that the suspects were believed to have committed the crime out of revenge due to incidents of taunting among the madrasa students and the suspects. According to him, six out of seven suspects tested positive for drugs, and two of them had previous criminal records related to rioting and stealing vehicles. All suspects were aged between 11 and 18 years old. On August 17, 2020, Muhammad Adli Shah Bin Mohd Yusry was found guilty of 23 counts of murder and was sentenced to detention at the pleasure of the Yang-Dipertuan Agong (YDPA) (The Malaysian King). (Scribd, 2021).

In 2019, a 16-year-old teenager was found dead, believed to have fallen from the third floor of a shop lot in Kuching, Sarawak after she conducted an online poll to decide if she should kill herself or not. According to online news portal Astro Awani, Padawan district police Chief Supt Aidil Bolhassan said the teenager had conducted the voting via Instagram. “As many as 69 per cent of the teenager’s Instagram friends had supported the decision for her to kill herself via a voting poll which was uploaded at around 3pm yesterday,” Aidil said. The teen had reportedly posted the headline “Really Important, Help Me Choose D/L” on the voting poll. “D” reportedly meant “die” while “L” stands for “live”. The teen had also uploaded a Facebook status that read: ‘WANNA QUIT F**KING LIFE I’M TIRED.’ “The teenager was believed to have felt stressed when her stepfather married a Vietnamese woman and seldom returned to their home,” Aidil was quoted as saying. Her body was found at about 8pm by a member of the public who then reported the discovery to the Batu Kawa Police Station. Aidil said the body was brought to the Sarawak General Hospital Forensic Department for a post-mortem, which was scheduled to take place this evening. No criminal elements were detected at the scene and the case has been classified as sudden death, he added. (Terrence Tang, 2019). In March 2020, Kuala Selangor police arrested a group of Form Three to Form Five students following a bullying incident at a local tahfiz school in Tanjong Karang. The arrest came after a male student was reportedly assaulted by a group of senior students at the religious school. The incident gained public

attention after a Facebook user claiming to be the victim's brother shared details of the attack on March 12, alleging that the victim suffered liver and spleen injuries as a result of the bullying and that the organs may be removed due to the severity of the damage. The local media, *Sinar Harian* reported Kuala Selangor deputy police chief, Deputy Superintendent Noor Janihan Nanyan, saying that the victim initially sought treatment at the Tanjong Karang Hospital before being transferred to Tengku Ampuan Rahimah Hospital in Klang, due to the severity of his injuries. In a later development, another local media *Harian Metro* reported that the assault might have been triggered by the victim's alleged use of an electronic cigarette. The report cited an unnamed source from the school claiming that a senior student, upon discovering the victim smoking a vape in the dormitory, became enraged, leading to the violent confrontation. (Yiswaree Palansamy, 2024). These are only few samples of reported cases involving bullying, aggression and harassment among students in the educational sectors in the country. There is a long list of similar reported cases which have been reported through the media for the last many years. These issues happen every year and the Malaysian public now demand serious steps be taken to address with the problem.

2.0 DEFINING BULLYING, AGGRESSION AND HARASSMENT AS WELL AS IDENTIFYING THE ROOT CAUSE OF THE PROBLEM

Before finding the steps to address with the issue concerning bullying, aggression and harassment, it is very important for us to locate its definition and composition first as well identifying the root cause which gives rise to the problems. What is bullying? Bullying is when people repeatedly and intentionally use words or actions against someone or a group of people to cause distress and risk to their wellbeing. These actions are usually done by people who have more influence or power over someone else, or who want to make someone else feel less powerful or helpless. Bullying is not the same as conflict between people (like having a fight) or disliking someone, even though people might bully each other because of conflict or dislike. Important for us to realize that bullying can happen anywhere. It can be in schools, university campus, at home, at work, in online social spaces, via text messaging or via email. It can be physical, verbal, emotional, and it also includes messages, public statements and behaviour online intended to cause distress or harm (also known as cyberbullying). But no matter what form bullying takes, the results can be the same namely such act cause severe distress and pain for the person being bullied. There are basically three types of well-known act of bullying namely face-to-face bullying, covert bullying and cyberbullying. Face-to-face bullying (sometimes referred to as direct bullying) involves physical actions such as punching or kicking or direct verbal actions such as name-calling and insulting. Covert bullying (sometimes referred to as indirect bullying) is less direct, but just as painful. It means bullying which isn't easily seen by others and is conducted out of sight, such as excluding people from groups or spreading lies or rumours. Because it is less obvious, it is often unacknowledged by adults. With the advancement of new technologies, bullying can also occur in cyber space. Such act is known as cyberbullying. Cyberbullying occurs through the use of information or communication technologies such Instant Messaging or chat, text messages, email and social networking sites or forums. It has many similarities with offline bullying, but it can also be anonymous, it can reach a wide audience, and sent or uploaded material can be difficult to remove. Most people who cyberbully also bully off-line. (Australian Human Rights Commission, 2024).

What is aggression? In psychology, aggression refers to a range of behaviours that can result in both physical and psychological harm to an individual, others, or objects in the environment. Aggression centres on hurting another person either physically or mentally. While every human being may feel aggressive on occasion, when aggression becomes pervasive or extreme, it may be a sign of an underlying mental health condition, a substance use disorder, or another medical issue. Aggressive behaviours can be physical, like beating, hitting, kicking, or stabbing another person. Damaging property is also a form of physical aggression. It can be verbal like mocking, name-calling, and yelling. It can also be relational, which is intended to harm another person's relationships. This can include spreading rumours and telling lies about someone else. It can also include passive-aggressive like ignoring someone during a social event or offering back-handed compliments. Passive-aggressive behaviour is usually intended to allow harm to come to someone, rather than causing harm directly. Psychological aggression can also be very damaging. Intimidating or verbally berating another person, for instance, are examples of verbal, mental, and emotional aggression. Cyberbullying is another form of non-physical aggression that can cause serious harm to others. (Kendra Cherry, 2022).

What is harassment? Harassment covers a wide range of behaviours of an offensive nature. It is commonly understood as behaviour that demeans, humiliates, and intimidates a person, and it is characteristically identified by its unlikelihood in terms of social and moral reasonableness. In the legal sense, these are behaviours that appear to be disturbing, upsetting, or threatening. Traditional forms evolve from discriminatory grounds, and have an effect of nullifying a person's rights or impairing a person from

benefiting from their rights. There are various types of harassment like physical harassment, psychological harassment, racial harassment, age harassment, sexual harassment, gender-based harassment and many more. When harassing behaviours become repetitive, it is defined as bullying.

After analysing the definition of bullying, aggression and harassment, it is very clear to us that all the mentioned acts are interconnected to each other. All the mentioned acts are bad and negative. The consequences of committing these mentioned acts are very detrimental to the victim and their family. Crucial to note, all the mentioned acts have criminal elements and need to be prevented at any cost. There cannot be any excuse to address these problems. Bullying, aggression and harassment is the acts of violence which need serious attention by everyone. Countries including Malaysia have developed much legislation addressing the problems. What is need now is strong enforcement of these legislations.

What is the root cause of the problems? What give rise to the issue of bullying, aggression and harassment in the educational sector? It is very hard to identify the exact cause which gives rise to these problems. However, several factors might play important role. Firstly, is the factor which attributed to the perpetrator themselves. The perpetrator might be brought up under violence environment which might affect his or her mental and emotional capability to differentiate between right and wrong behaviour. The perpetrator might also face with health issue like mental or psychological problem which affect his or her ability to think rationally. Secondly, factor which attributed to surrounding environment. The perpetrator might be influence by the surrounding which exposes him or her to the act of violence. Bad parenting or uncaring parent and guardian, living in bad neighbourhood, socializing with bad friends, watching too much violence movies or films and others which could potentially affect the character and personality of the perpetrator towards violence. Lack of understanding and awareness over the issue could also give rise to the problems. Thirdly, weak enforcement of the existing laws which address bullying, aggression and harassment. Many countries including Malaysia have developed many laws to regulate the issue over bullying, aggression and harassment. But, all these laws become futile if the enforcement of such laws are weak. The victim could make a report to the relevant authorities. However, the main question which need to be ask here is that will the relevant authorities accept the report, make the necessary investigation immediately and arrest the suspect for further investigation and prosecution in the court of law? There are cases where the victim lodged a report to the relevant authority, but no much progress been made towards the report which been lodged earlier. There are also cases where the relevant authority declared such case to be held No Further Action (NFA) which means the report will not be proceed for legal action in the court. (Rameiza Wahid, 2020 and Hariz Mohd, 2021). All these make the victim of bullying, aggression and harassment demoralized and having no desire any longer to bring a legal action against the perpetrator. Fourthly, bad management. Bullying, aggression and harassment will not happen unless the perpetrator knows that the place is not being monitor properly by the management or no action will be taken against them by the management. Schools and universities management should play active role when dealing with these problems. It is because many of the reported incidents involving bullying, aggression and harassment happen within the schools and universities compound like inside classroom, at canteen, on playground, toilet, store room and dormitory. The management should properly monitor their premise to ensure no illegal activity taking place. The management should also draft a clear and comprehensive policy to address these problems effectively. If the management really care over the safety and well-being of their students, the management should engage with the civil societies and non – governmental organizations (NGOs) to educate and create more awareness activity and program to the students about the issue over bullying, aggression and harassment.

3.0 FINDING THE SOLUTIONS

Bullying, aggression and harassment is a serious act which need serious attention by everyone. Everybody needs to cooperate to find any possible solutions to address with the problems effectively. People should not point finger at anyone when dealing with the problems. We need to remembered, the effects of bullying, aggression and harassment is very detrimental to everyone especially to the victim. The life of the victim who are facing bullying, aggression and harassment will be badly affected. The victim will be suffered silently having the pressure emotionally and mentally as well as will feel traumatizes with the horrible experience which they have gone through. If the no early step been taken to deal with the problem, the victim will become depress and eventually could lead to suicide. Bullying, aggression and harassment is a crime and should be stop and prevented at any cost. There are several ways to deal with the issue, one of it is through legislation. The country needs to have strong and comprehensive legislation in order to deal with the issue of bullying, aggression and harassment. In recent years, the Malaysian government has legislated few laws to address with such problems. In 2022, the country has enacted specific law addressing the issue concerning sexual harassment. The act is known as the Anti-Sexual Harassment Act 2022 [Act 840]. The Act, which was first tabled in Parliament in December 2021, passed by the Dewan Rakyat (House of Representatives) in

July 2022 and gazette as an Act in October 2022. (Mohd Fadli, 2022). The Act provides a right of redress for any person who has been sexually harassed, the establishment of a Tribunal for Anti-Sexual Harassment, and to raise awareness and prevent the occurrence of sexual harassment. Anyone who feel that their right been violated can utilized such act to seek remedy. Bear in mind, Section 7 (1) Anti-Sexual Harassment Act 2022 [Act 840] states “The Tribunal shall have jurisdiction to hear and determine any complaint of sexual harassment made by any person”. Section 2 of the Anti-Sexual Harassment Act 2022 [Act 840] define sexual harassment as “Any unwanted conduct of a sexual nature, in any form, whether verbal, non – verbal, visual, gestural or physical, directed at a person which is reasonably offensive or humiliating or is a threat to his well – being”. From the definition given under Section 2, sexual harassment can take place in several forms like verbal sexual harassment which includes offensive or suggestive remarks, comments, jokes, jesting (jokes), kidding, sounds, and questioning, non – verbal sexual harassment which includes leering or ogling (Staring) with suggestive overtones, licking lips or holding or eating food provocatively, hand signal or sign language denoting sexual activity, and persistent flirting, visual sexual harassment which includes showing pornographic materials, drawing sex – based sketches or writing se based letters, and sexual exposure, psychological sexual harassment which includes repeated unwanted social invitations, relentless proposals for dates or physical intimacy, and physical sexual harassment which includes inappropriate touching, patting (rubbing), pinching, stroking, brushing up against the body, hugging, kissing, fondling, and sexual assault. Sexual harassment can happen at any places like workplace, school, university, inside public transports, recreational park, and others. Besides legislation, education also play important role to put an end to the issue of sexual harassment. Though this particular Act specifically addressing the issue concerning harassment which is sexual in nature, yet it is a good start for the country in addressing with the issue concerning bullying, aggression and harassment. There is a promise made by the government to make improvement over this particular Act in the coming future. (The Star, 2024).

Amendments were also been made to the country criminal legislation namely the Penal Code [Act 574]. In 2023, the Malaysian government has decided to make the act of stalking a crime. (Ming Teoh, 2023). Individuals who is found guilty of stalking, regardless of whether they are men or women, can now be jailed for up to three years or fined, or both. This is after the country Dewan Rakyat (House of Representatives) on 29 March 2023 passed the Penal Code (Amendment) Bill 2023 with a new section 507A introduced into the Penal Code [Act 574] for the offence of stalking. This particular Bill has also been passed by the Dewan Negara (House of Senate) on 7 April 2023. The section states that whoever repeatedly by any act of harassment, intending to cause, or knowing or ought to know that the act is likely to cause distress, fear or alarm to any person or the person’s safety, commits the offence of stalking. Deputy Minister in the Prime Minister’s Department (Law and Institutional Reform) Ramkarpal Singh said the amendment is to protect victims of stalking, both women and men. Also, been passed is the amendments to the Criminal Procedure Code [Act 593] which include a new Section 98A to protect victims from suspected stalkers. A survey cone by a local research company and the Women’s Aid Organisation (WOA) in 2020 among 1008 respondents showed that stalking was rampant in the country where some 36% of Malaysians experienced being stalked and felt fear, 12% were threatened while 17% suffered injuries. At the same time, 69% of Malaysians also agreed that stalking should be a crime. There are many countries already declare stalking as a crime. With this latest amendment to the existing laws, Malaysia joins a minority of countries in Asia that have legislation criminalizing stalking on their books. India identified stalking as a crime in 2013 along with a set of new anti-rape laws, while Singapore did the same in 2014 with the introduction of an anti-harassment law. In 2021, Japan strengthened its anti-stalking laws to broaden the scope of offending acts, which now include installing GPS tracking devices on targets’ cars and harassing them via written letters. People need to be aware over the current development on this issue. People in the country need to be constantly be educate not to misuse any existing technologies including using camera or any recording devices for crimes or immoral purpose. Technology can make us more responsible if we use it wisely.

In early December 2024, the country Dewan Rakyat (House of Representatives) passed the Penal Code (Amendment) (No. 2) Bill 2024, to address all forms of bullying, including cyberbullying. The Bill, tabled by the country Minister in the Prime Minister’s Department (Law and Institutional Reform) Datuk Seri Azalina Othman Said, was approved by a majority voice vote. In her closing remarks, Azalina emphasised that the amendment does not intend to curtail freedom of speech but serves as a preventive mechanism to combat harassment and safeguard society, particularly children. “This amendment is not solely punitive but also aims to educate, protect, and prevent. It is a crucial step toward fostering a more civil society that respects the dignity of every individual,” she stated. Azalina added that the amendment addresses legal gaps, including the absence of specific provisions in the Penal Code [Act 574] against bullying and cyberbullying. The Bill introduces a new subsection, 507D (2), which aims to criminalise any act involving the use of threatening, insulting, or defamatory words or communications with the intent to provoke someone, resulting in harm to

themselves or others. This subsection prescribes a penalty of imprisonment for up to one year, a fine, or both upon conviction. Additionally, if the provoked individual attempts suicide or dies by suicide due to such provocation, the proposed offence carries a punishment of imprisonment for up to 10 years, a fine, or both. Meanwhile, the Dewan Rakyat (House of Representatives) also passed the Criminal Procedure Code (Amendment) (No. 2) Bill 2024, to align with the amendments to the Penal Code. Among its provisions are regulations on the requirement for arrest warrants, the duration of the warrant or summons validity, the classification of offences as bailable or non-bailable, the conditions for compounding offences, and the maximum penalties for offences related to bullying. (The Sun Daily, 2024). In tabling the amendments, law and institutional reform minister Azalina Othman Said also said the new laws include an “Esha clause”, which criminalises those who provoke others to harm themselves. The “Esha clause” is named in remembrance of Rajeswary Appahu, an influencer who had taken her own life after being harassed online. “Current laws do not adequately address psychological or emotional threats, especially those carried out through digital means like social media or messaging apps,” Azalina said. She also defended the lack of mens rea (intent) in Section 507C of the Penal Code to make sure that the act of bullying is thoroughly addressed, regardless if there was intent or not. Azalina said making this law a strict liability offence, or a law that does not require prosecutors to prove intent by the offender, was decided to make sure offenders do not exploit legal loopholes to avoid prosecution. “Bullying today is more complex, and we must ensure the law captures actions that cause harm, even when intent cannot be clearly proven,” she said. Azalina said the accused would be fairly treated, as the new laws allow them to defend themselves by proving that they had no reasonable grounds to believe their actions would be perceived as harmful or distressing. (Predeep Nambiar, 2024, Iylia Marsya Iskandar, Hana Naz Harun, 2024 and Rahimy Rahim, Ragananthini Vethasalam and Gerard Gimino, 2024).

Besides these, the Malaysian government can also consider to amend our existing Education Act 1996 [Act 550] or creating a new specific law which can specifically address the issue of bullying, aggression and harassment more comprehensively in our country. We can learn from what had been implemented in the United Kingdom where by virtue of Section 89 of the Education and Inspections Act 2006, it provides for an anti-bullying policy to be made for all state schools and to be made available to parents as well. It has been widely believed that creating and developing a strong and proper policy against bullying in schools and universities would be the first important step in creating high awareness among pupils at early age to understand the ugly nature of bullying and would eventually deter themselves from getting involved with such act. Through this simple yet clear policy, it will also establish a climate in which bullying is not tolerable and acceptable. Similar approach has also been implemented in the United States of America, where all 50 states in the US already have their own anti-bullying laws. This law is not going to abolish bullying, but it does bring attention to the aggressors, and they let the aggressors know their harmful behaviours will never be tolerated. Some of the written policies in the US even require disciplinary procedures to be made specifically to deal with bullying incident while others mandate that schools track and report for every bullying incident that occur. A growing number of states in the US also currently require schools to employ someone specially trained in anti-bullying education. The school and university management need to take the issue of bullying, aggression and harassment seriously and developed comprehensive plans to deal with such issue effectively. The school and university management need to develop a clear and comprehensive in-house policy which can address bullying, aggression and harassment efficiently. School and university management need to developed a clear procedural process for victim to lodge their complain and for the witness to come forward to give testimony and evidence. The policy needs to define the act of bullying, aggression and harassment, categories of bullying, aggression and harassment as well as the emergency contact number for the victim to seek immediate help. The idea to have a hotline contact number has also been proposed. (Anne Mohammad, 2024). Such policy needs to be explained to students and staffs so that everybody has basic idea over the issue of bullying, aggression and harassment. There is also a proposal to put CCTV in the premises to monitor the students. (Free Malaysia Today, 2024). However, the idea to rely on CCTV might be subjected to scrutiny by many peoples due to the lack of believe over its effectiveness and possibility of breaching the privacy of the students and misused. School and university management along with the student’s association and relevant non-governmental organization (NGO) need to work together to address the issue of bullying, aggression and harassment to the students. They need to constantly organize educational talks and conduct awareness programs which highlighted the issue of bullying, aggression and harassment to the students. Students in school and university need to be exposed and be educating over the issue of bullying, aggression and harassment if we want to reduce or put an end to the problems. The time has also come for us to take a bold step to put an end to the issue or at least take some efforts to control the problem before it becomes out of control. If no drastic steps been taken from now, it would not only harm the victim but it will also affect the reputation of the country education system and Malaysia position as the educational hub in the region and internationally.

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